

Effect of different oral oxytetracycline treatment regimes on selection of antimicrobial resistant coliforms in nursery pigs

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16 **Abstract**

17 A major concern derived from using antimicrobials in pig production is the development of resistance.
18 This study aimed to assess the impact of selected combinations of oral dose and duration of treatment
19 with oxytetracycline (OTC) on selection of tetracycline resistant (TET-R) coliforms recovered from
20 swine feces. The work encompassed two studies: 1) OTC 5 mg/kg and 20 mg/kg were administered
21 to nursery pigs for 3 and 10 days, respectively, under controlled experimental conditions, and 2) 10
22 mg/kg, 20 mg/kg and 30 mg/kg OTC were given to a higher number of pigs for 6, 3 and 2 days,
23 respectively, under field conditions. Statistical modelling was applied to analyze trends in the
24 proportion of TET-R coliforms. In the experimental study, no statistical difference in proportion of
25 TET-R coliforms was observed between treatments at the end of the trial (day 18) and compared to
26 day 0. In the field study, treatment had a significant effect on the proportion of TET-R bacteria two
27 days after the end of treatment (2dAT) with the regimes “low dose-six days” and “medium dose-three
28 days” yielding the highest and lowest proportions of TET-R strains, respectively. No indication of
29 co-selection for ampicillin- and sulphonamide -R bacteria was observed for any treatment at 2dAT.
30 By the end of the nursery period, the proportion of TET-R bacteria was not significantly different
31 between treatments and compared to day 0. Our results suggest that similar resistance levels might
32 be obtained by using different treatment regimes regardless of the combinations of oral dose-duration
33 of treatment.

34 **Keywords:** *E. coli*, pig, antimicrobial resistance, oxytetracycline treatment regime, co-selection.

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36 **1. Introduction**

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38 Antimicrobial resistance is recognized as a global health problem, and the World Health Organization
39 considers it as one of the top health challenges facing the 21st century (FDA, 2000; CDC, 2014). The
40 persistent increase in resistance is alarming, and the occurrence of high resistance levels continues to
41 threaten the ability of both doctors and veterinarians to treat infections.

42 For many years, the association between antimicrobial resistant bacteria in humans and antimicrobial
43 use in food animals has been debated (Jones and Ricke, 2003; Phillips et al., 2004; Chiller et al., 2004;
44 Alpharma, 2007; Cox and Ricci, 2008; Falgenhauer et al., 2016). Based on a large amount of data,
45 however, it is now evident that use of antimicrobials in food animals impacts human health through
46 direct transfer of resistant bacteria, and more distantly through the food chain and the environment
47 (Levy et al., 1976; Holmberg et al., 1984; Hummel et al., 1986; Fey et al., 2000). Since it is unrealistic
48 and unethical for animal welfare reasons to completely avoid the use of antimicrobials in intensive
49 livestock production, it is important to identify the anti-microbial applications in livestock that might
50 have the highest impact on human health, and to minimize the development of resistance without
51 compromising treatment efficacy.

52 *Escherichia coli* is a common facultative anaerobic bacterium in the intestinal microbiota of humans
53 and animals (Karami et al., 2006), and it is therefore one of the commensal bacteria commonly used
54 as an indicator in different types of studies in animals, humans, and food products (Karami et al.,
55 2006; EFSA, 2012). Its ubiquitous presence in mammals and indications of resistance occurrence in
56 the bacterium make it a good candidate for studies on antimicrobial selection pressure in the
57 population (Vieira et al., 2011).

58 In Denmark, the swine sector accounted for ca. 80% of the veterinary use of antimicrobials in 2012
59 and tetracycline was the most frequently used drug in pig production (Apley et al., 1998; McDermott
60 et al., 2002; DANMAP, 2013), commonly administered to treat intestinal diseases in nursery pigs
61 (Roberts, 1996; DANMAP, 2013). Approximately 36% of *E. coli* isolates were tetracycline resistant
62 (TET-R) in the Danish antimicrobial resistance surveillance system of pigs in 2012 (DANMAP,
63 2013). Furthermore, this surveillance has shown high levels of TET-R *E. coli* (over 30%) over the
64 past five years, suggesting that TET-R *E. coli* are endemic in the pig production. Tetracycline is also
65 used in humans, accounting for 11% of the total consumption of anti-microbials in the Danish health
66 care sector in 2012 (DANMAP, 2013), and resistance to this antimicrobial is very common in *E. coli*
67 from humans (Calva et al., 1996; Karami et al., 2006; Marshall and Levy, 2011).

68 In previous studies, where a mathematical model was developed and used to simulate selection of
69 tetracycline resistance following treatment (Græsbøll et al., 2014; Ahmad et al., 2015), it was
70 predicted that all the doses tested led to a temporary advantage for TET-R strains compared to the
71 sensitive ones in the intestine of nursery pigs. It was also predicted that the total amount of antibiotic
72 used and the duration of treatment affected selection of resistance, as well as the time it took for the
73 intestinal flora to get back to equilibrium. Based on these observations, the aim of the present work,
74 encompassing two in vivo studies, was to analyze the effect of different tetracycline treatment regimes
75 on emergence and selection of TET-R coliforms in the gut of nursery pigs. Also, co-selection for
76 ampicillin (AMP) and sulphonamide (SUL) resistant bacteria was investigated.

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81 **2. Material and methods**

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83 *2.1 Animals, experimental setup and ethical issues*

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85 Two studies, an experimental trial and a study under field conditions were performed.

86 For the experimental study, 24 seven-to-eight weeks old nursery cross-bred sex-mixed pigs (11–18
87 kg) were purchased from a specific-pathogen-free farm in Denmark. The animals were housed in a
88 level 1 isolation unit at University of Copenhagen and weighed at least once a week. Animal
89 experiments were carried out according to the Animals Scientific Act and after having obtained the
90 license and approval of the Danish National Animal Experiment Inspectorate (license no. 2009/ 561-
91 1675). At the end of the study, all pigs were euthanized by captive bolt pistol penetration followed
92 by bleeding.

93 Pigs in the experimental trial were divided into five groups housed in five well-separated pens
94 avoiding contact between them. After one week of acclimatization, four groups including five pigs
95 each received a specific oxytetracycline (OTC) treatment as follows: groups 1 and 2; low dose of
96 antibiotic (5 mg/kg) for three and 10 days (Do5.Dur3 and Do5.Dur10), groups 3 and 4; high dose of
97 antibiotic (20 mg/kg) for three and 10 days (Do20.Dur3 and Do20.Dur10). Group 5, was not treated
98 (Do0.Dur0) (Table 1). Terramycin®Vet. 20% solution (Orion Pharm, Copenhagen, Denmark) was
99 orally and individually administered to all pigs at the specific dose in nutri-drink (Nutricia, Allerød,
100 Denmark).

101 For the field study, 120 pigs were randomly selected at one specific farm in Denmark where pigs were
102 housed under regular pig production conditions. Permission to perform these experiments was granted
103 by the Danish Medicines Agency (license no. 2011090862/2012053751) and a written “Owner
104 informed consent” was signed by the owner of the herd involved in the study.

105 The nursery pigs used in the field study were divided into six pens containing 20 pigs each. Treatment
106 with OTC was started at week four after weaning. Pigs in different pens received the following OTC
107 treatments (in duplicate): groups 1 and 2; low dose of antibiotic (10 mg/kg) for six days (Do10.Dur6),
108 groups 3 and 4; medium dose (20 mg/kg) for three days (Do20.Dur3) and groups 5 and 6; high dose
109 (30 mg/kg) for two days (Do30.Dur2). It was not possible to include a control group under field
110 conditions. All treatments were implemented at the pen level, and were randomly allocated to pen by
111 draw. Terramycin®Vet. 20% was administered orally through drinking water, through a dosing
112 pump, and it was controlled that all the medicine was consumed within 24 h (Larsen et al., 2016).

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114 *2.2. Collection and microbiological analysis of fecal samples*

115

116 Fecal samples (ca. 5 g) were collected from the rectum of all the pigs prior to antimicrobial treatment
117 (day 0) and every second day over a period of 18 days (experimental study) and before starting the
118 treatment (day 0), at two and 10 days after having finished the treatment (2dAT and 10dAT), as well
119 as by the end of the nursery period (EN; 20 days after day 0) (field study). At every collection time
120 CFU counts were performed. For this, serial 10-fold dilutions in PBS were prepared and inoculated
121 on MacConkey agar (Oxoid, Thermo Scientific, Roskilde, Denmark) without antibiotic and on
122 MacConkey agar supplemented with 16 µg/ml TET (both studies) and 16 µg/ml AMP or 250 µg/ml
123 SUL (field study). Antibiotics were purchased from Sigma (Sigma-Aldrich, Copenhagen, Denmark).
124 All counts were determined by the spot method (Cavaco et al., 2008). Briefly, 20 µl of each dilution
125 was inoculated as a spot on two plates, followed by 24 h of incubation at 37 °C. Deep red colonies
126 with a diameter of > 0.5 mm were counted. The species of one hundred such colonies had previously
127 been tested by MaldiToff and all of them were shown to be *E. coli* (Katakweba et al., 2015). Such a

128 control was not performed in the current study, and we will use the term coliforms, even though they
129 are likely to be *E. coli*.

130

131 2.3. Statistical analysis

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133 Average log₁₀ transformed CFU of TET-R coliforms was compared between treatment groups
134 (experimental study) using ANOVA with Turkey's multiple comparison test in GraphPad Prism,
135 version 6.0 (GraphPad software, La Jolla, USA). Statistical modelling of CFU data was performed
136 using a generalized linear model in the statistical soft-ware R (Version 3.2.5). The count data was
137 assumed to be Poisson distributed, and in case of over dispersion this was relaxed to so-called
138 quasi-poisson. The dilution was used as offset for each count. For the two distributional
139 assumptions, ChiSq- and F-test with Pearson residuals (Venables and Ripley, 2002) were
140 performed, respectively. In all models interactions with the presence of antimicrobials were the
141 focus. The CFU count in every sample was included as a nuisance parameter in all models. CFU
142 counts were log transformed using the natural logarithm used as a link function. A *P*-value (*P*) <
143 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

144 The analysis was performed for tetracycline resistance (experimental and field study) as well as for
145 co-selection of other antimicrobial resistances (field study). If three or more dilutions from the same
146 sample on the same medium had positive counts, then, only the two least diluted counts were included
147 to reduce over-dispersion. Only samples having counts both with and without antimicrobials in the
148 media were included. For all individual samples an estimate of the proportion of resistant bacteria
149 was made. If the proportion was above 100%, then the probability of being below 100% was
150 calculated, and the sample was discarded if this probability was less than 0.1% (see Discussion).

151 The total CFU and CFU of resistant strains were also estimated for each treatment at each day in the
152 experimental study. This was done using a generalized linear model with counts from individual
153 pens on the individual days.

154

155 **3. Results**

156

157 *3.1. Effect of different OTC treatment regimes on selection of TET-R coliforms under experimental* 158 *conditions*

159

160 An experimental study was first conducted in order to analyze which combinations of doses and
161 duration of treatment might result in less development of resistance. Due to ethical reasons and cost
162 of the experiments, only four (control group) or five pigs (groups subjected to treatment) were
163 included in each treatment group.

164 Trends in CFU counts of total coliforms were analyzed over time for the four treatment groups (Fig.
165 1A). Slightly different trends in CFU counts of total coliforms were observed between the four
166 treatments regimes, however, these were not statistically significant (Fig. 1A). The general trend was
167 a decrease of the overall coliform population in all the groups regardless of the treatment over time
168 (from day 0 to day 18).

169 On the second day of treatment, a peak (not significant increase compared to day 0) in total number
170 of coliforms was observed in three out of the four treatment groups (both groups treated with low
171 doses and the group treated with high dose for a short period). In the group treated with a high dose
172 for 10 days, the peak (not significant increase compared to day 0) was observed on day eight. In all
173 treatment groups, the peak was followed by a decrease (not significant) on the following time point.
174 At this time point, the CFU counts were not significantly different from those obtained at day 0 either.

175 In the non-treated control group a peak like the one detected for the treated groups was not observed
176 at any time point.

177 The number of TET-R coliforms showed a similar trend to the one detected for the total numbers of
178 coliforms (Fig. 1B), indicating that the peak in total coliforms during the treatment period in all groups
179 was caused by selective growth of TET-R coliforms. The average CFU count of TET-R coliforms
180 was not significantly different between groups on day 0. On day four, where short duration treatments
181 (three days) were over, only the average count of TET-R strains for the low dose for three days
182 treatment group (Do5.Dur3) was not significantly different from the average count of the control
183 group. On day 12, two days after the long treatments (10 days) ended, the average count of none of
184 the groups was significantly different from the average count in the control group, and the low dose
185 for three days treatment group (Do5.Dur3) showed a significantly lower average count than the high
186 dose for 10 days group (Do20.Dur10). The highest numbers of TET-R coliforms by the end of the
187 experiment (day 18) were detected in the two groups treated with high dose (significantly higher than
188 the low dose treatment groups). However, at this time point, the average count of TET-R isolates of
189 none of the treatment groups was statistically different from the average count in the control group.
190 The group subjected to the low dose for three days regime showed a significantly lower average count
191 than the three other treatment groups.

192 The proportion of TER-R coliforms over time was also analyzed (Fig. 1C). Before the start of the
193 treatment, approximately half of the coliform population was TET-R. In the groups treated with
194 high doses of TET, the proportion of TET-R coliforms approaches 100% shortly after treatment. On
195 day four, a significant increase of the proportion of TET- R strains was observed compared to day 0
196 in all the groups, no matter the treatment. On day 18 (end of the experimental trial), no significant
197 differences were observed for any of the groups compared to day 0.

198 Statistical modeling of the results showed that the proportion of TET-R strains did not vary
199 significantly over time between groups ($P > 0,05$) but on the final day of the experiment (day 18) the
200 two groups receiving the high dose showed the highest proportion of TET-R coliforms.
201 Contrary to this, the model showed that the CFU/g varied greatly between animals and over time (P
202 < 0.05), which indicated that each pig responded individually to the treatment.

203

204 *3.2 Effect of OTC treatment regimes on selection of TET-R coliforms under field conditions*

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206 While the results of the experimental study lacked clear results in terms of statistically significant
207 results on the proportion of TET-R coliforms after treatment, the trend was that the group subjected
208 to the regime low dose for a short period would have significantly fewer TET-R coliforms compared
209 to the rest of the groups ([Fig. 1C](#)). Since we saw very little difference between the two groups that
210 received high dose, we hypothesized that dose was more important than duration of treatment with
211 regard to selection for resistance. In order to test this hypothesis, we performed a field study, where
212 all pigs received the same total amount of OCT, but split over different number of treatment days.
213 This allowed us to study the effect of dose without the con-founding factor “total amount of
214 antimicrobial”, since all pigs received the same total amount of OCT. The number of pigs and the
215 conditions used were those used under regular pig production conditions in Denmark.

216 Also under field conditions, the trend in total numbers of coliforms was very similar in all the groups
217 and with no significant difference between groups at any time-point ([Fig. 2A](#)). A steep significant
218 decrease was observed in the first weeks after weaning (between the start of the nursery period and
219 day 0) in all the three treatment groups. At 2dAT a small peak (not significant increase compared to
220 day 0) was detected in the treatment groups; Do10.Du6 and Do20.Du3, followed by a decrease
221 afterwards. At the end of the nursery period, the CFU counts of coliforms for all the groups were

222 significantly lower from those detected at the start of the nursery period (SN) ($P < 0,05$) although not
223 significantly different from the counts at day 0 (Fig. 2A).

224 A similar trend in CFU counts, with no significant difference between groups at any time point, was
225 observed for TET-R coliforms (Fig. 2B). Also here, a small peak (not significant increase compared
226 to day 0) was detected at 2dAT for Do10.Du6 and Do20.Du3, followed by a decrease.

227 As shown for the experimental trial, the proportion of TET-R coli-forms was already between 20 and
228 40% of the population before the start of the treatment (day 0) (Fig. 2C). The proportion of TET-R in-
229 creased as a response to treatment, however, at the end of the nursery period, there was not significant
230 different in proportions between groups.

231 The changes in proportion of TET-R coliforms following tetracycline treatment was subjected to
232 statistical modeling. A total of 2158 counts were made of which 142 were left out due to obvious
233 mistakes in dilution series and another 36 counts were left out due to lack of completeness (lacking
234 data for either total coliforms or TET-R coliforms) or infeasible proportion of resistance (see Material
235 and methods). The remaining 1980 counts were included in the analysis. A three-way interaction with
236 antimicrobial, time point and treatment was included in the model to describe the change in the
237 proportion of TET-R coliforms. There was clear over-dispersion of data, and the dispersion parameter
238 for the quasi-poisson model was estimated to be 7.61. The three-way interaction was significant ($P <$
239 0.05), meaning that evolution in proportion of TET-R coliforms was different over the tested time
240 points between treatments.

241 To test the influence of the treatment on the proportion of TET-R bacteria at the end of the nursery
242 period, the samples on day 0 and EN were merged and tested against the full model. It was found that
243 treatment did not change the proportion of TET-R significantly ($P > 0.05$). Furthermore, it was tested
244 if there was an immediate effect of the treatment by comparing day 0 and EN with 2dAT. Here a

245 significant difference was found ($P < 0.05$), meaning that treatment in-creased the proportion of TET-
246 R bacteria immediately after treatment.

247 The OTC treatment Do20.Dur3 led to the lowest proportion of TET-R coliforms at this time point.
248 By the end of the nursery period the pro-portion was back to the same level as before starting the
249 treatment. This observation was independent of the treatment group ([Fig. 2C](#)).

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251 *3.3 Analysis of co-selection of AMP- and SUL -R bacteria*

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253 Selection with one antimicrobial can also promote selection for other resistances since they might be
254 co-localized on the same genetic element (22). Therefore we also analyzed the effect of the OTC
255 treatments regimes on co-selection for AMP- or SUL -R bacteria at 2dAT (time point where an effect
256 of tetracycline treatment was observed) ([Fig. 3](#)).

257 For the analysis of co-resistance to AMP, 2154 counts were made of which 155 were left out due to
258 mistakes in the dilution series and another 44 counts were left out due to lack of completeness or
259 infeasible proportion of resistance. The remaining 1955 counts were included in the analysis. As for
260 the TET model the counts expressed over-dispersion. The three-way interaction was not significant
261 ($P > 0.05$). When comparing the proportion of AMP-R coliform at 2dAT to day 0, no significant
262 difference was observed, contrary to the results obtained for TET-R bacteria ($P > 0.05$). Further, the
263 proportion of AMP-R bacteria did not change significantly at later time points. The estimated pro-
264 portion was 53% (95% CI [45%; 63%]). In the final model for AMP-R, the dispersion parameter was
265 estimated to be 36.2.

266 For a similar analysis of SUL-R, 2143 counts were made of which 148 were left out as two less
267 diluted counts were made and another 34 counts were left out due to lack of completeness or infeasible
268 proportion of resistance. The remaining 1961 counts were included in the analysis. As for the TET

269 model the counts expressed over-dispersion. As shown for AMP, no significant difference was
270 observed for SUL-R proportions of coliforms at 2dAT compared to day 0 ($P > 0.05$) (not shown). As
271 expected, the proportion of SUL-R bacteria did not change significantly at the rest of the time points
272 tested as a consequence of tetracycline treatment, irrespective of the treatment regime (not shown).
273 The estimated proportion of SUL-R in coliforms was 58% (95% CI [51%; 66%]). In the final model
274 for SUL-R, the dispersion parameter was estimated to be 21.7.
275 For all three antimicrobials a full model was estimated, where each sample was allowed to have its
276 own proportion of resistant bacteria – these models did not show sign of over-dispersion. For all three
277 anti-microbials the full models were significantly better than the reduced models presented above.
278 This means that there was a large and highly significant pig-to-pig variation in response to OTC
279 treatment.

280

281 **4. Discussion**

282

283 Treatment with one or more antimicrobials is necessary for cure of diseases in livestock and therefore
284 for animal welfare reasons (Levy and Marshall 2004; Marshall and Levy, 2011). Thus, careful
285 investigations of dosing factors, such as treatment duration and drug concentration, are of relevance
286 in order to provide optimal treatment protocols which may help keep the occurrence and development
287 of resistance at the lowest possible level. In the present study the effect of different OTC treatment
288 regimes with variation in oral dose and duration of treatment on the selection of TET-R strains was
289 analyzed. Since resistance genes can be harbored on the same mobile genetic element, co-selection
290 for AMP and SUL resistances was also investigated.

291 The work was divided in two in vivo experiments, a first one under experimental conditions followed
292 by a second one carried out as a field study. Results showed that a high proportion of the coliforms

293 present in the gut of the nursery pigs in Denmark are TET-R (data derived from both studies) (Figs.
294 1C, 2C), AMP-R and SUL-R (field study) (Fig. 3B). These data support previously observed selection
295 of such resistant bacteria in pig production in Denmark and other countries due to the use of these
296 antibiotics for several decades (Martinez and Baquero, 2000; Lipsitch et al., 2000; DANMAP, 2013;
297 Jumbe et al., 2003; Levy and Marshall, 2004; Opatowski et al., 2011). This may be of relevance for
298 the conclusions of the current study since there is less “room” for further selection of resistant
299 coliforms when the starting level is high. Over the time span of the experimental study (18 days), no
300 statis-tical difference was observed in the proportion of TET-R coliforms be-tween the OTC treatment
301 regimes. Due to large pig-to-pig variation, the estimated proportion of TET-R bacteria remained
302 statistically constant over time according to the model performed, despite the total number of TET-R
303 coliforms was significantly different between groups at certain time points. Overall, our results are in
304 disagreement with previous studies (Levy and Marshall 2004; Opatowski et al., 2011; Spicknall et
305 al., 2013), however, also in our studies a trend was observed, with the high dose treatments
306 (Do20.Dur10 and Do20.Dur3) leading to the highest proportion of TET-R coliforms by the end of
307 the trial (day 18) (Fig. 1C), and differences with previous studies may partly be due to the rigorous
308 statistical approach performed in the current study. Care should be taken not to over-interpret the
309 trend observation with regard to the importance of dose versus duration of treatment, since results
310 were not statistically significant. This may, however, be because only five pigs were included in each
311 group. Furthermore, it should be noted that the step to the next dose level was large (from 20 mg/kg
312 to 5 mg/ kg). There may be an optimum of dose/duration combination for at given TET-MIC
313 distribution in a population, and further studies are needed to establish that combination for the
314 current population of TET-R coliforms in Danish pigs.

315 An important observation from this study was that pigs reacted differently to the same treatment,
316 causing a variation, which tended to be larger than the variation caused by different treatments. We

317 have previously shown that Danish nursery pigs contain up to 11 different *E. coli* strains when 50
318 colonies per pig were type by rep-PCR, but with large variation between pigs (Herrero-Fresno et al.,
319 2015). The span in MICs for TET-R *E. coli* from Danish pigs, which make up the largest proportion
320 of coliforms counted by our method, have been reported to be between 0.25 and 512 mg/l with
321 peaks at 0.5 mg/l for the sensitive part of the population and 32–68 mg/l for the resistant part
322 (Ahmad et al., 2015). It is unknown how this span is represented in individual pigs, but large
323 differences are bound to cause large differences in response to treatment with regard to selection of
324 TET-R coliforms. Probably for this reason, in all statistical models a high over-dispersion was
325 observed, which resulted in using the quasi-poisson family. Typical sources of over-dispersion are
326 sources of variation that are not included in the model. In the present study it was assumed that all
327 pigs in the same treatment group, the study units, had the same proportion of resistant bacteria at
328 each time point.

329 Under field conditions, an statistical significant effect of treatment on development of TET-R *E. coli*
330 was demonstrated at 2dAT compared to day 0, and the low dose-6 days (Do10.Dur6) treatment led
331 to a higher proportion of TET-R bacteria compared to the other regimes at this time point (Fig. 2C).
332 Even though there was not a significant effect of treatment on proportion of *E. coli* TET-R bacteria at
333 time 10dAT and at end of the nursery period compared to day 0, the trend was that the treatment
334 regime (Do10.Dur6) led to the highest proportion of TET-R coliforms at these time points (Fig. 2C).
335 Do20.Dur3 regime (the one leading to the second highest proportion of TET-R coliforms on day 18
336 of the experimental trial) yielded the lowest proportion of TET-R bacteria at 2dAT in the field study
337 (Fig. 2C). In general, one should put more emphasis on the results of the field study, since it
338 encompasses the natural variation in dose between pigs that are flock treated with the antimicrobial.
339 In the field study, it was also demonstrated that selection with TET did not significantly affect
340 development of AMP- and SUL -R bacteria at 2dAT (time point where an effect on treatment on

341 selection of TET-R bacteria was detected). Therefore, at this time point, co-selection for AMP and
342 SUL resistances is discarded.

343 Concerning duration of treatment, a mathematical simulation study concluded that short duration of
344 TET administration should be prefer-able in order to reduce selection for TET-resistance, since less
345 time under treatment would reduce the competitive growth of the R-strains (Ahmad et al., 2015). The
346 authors concluded that more prolonged treatment resulted in an increased occurrence of resistance
347 and therefore it took longer to return to equilibrium (Ahmad et al., 2015). It has previously been
348 demonstrated that it might also be possible to reduce the duration of treatment with a higher daily
349 dose level to achieve the desired efficacy and lower resistance levels (Geli et al., 2012). Our results
350 are in accordance with these predictions, but only at the specific time point 2dAT. Thus, in the field
351 study the medium-dose for three days treatment regime (Do20.Dur3) led to the lowest TET-R bacteria
352 at 2dAT compared to day 0 followed by the high-dose regime (Do30.Dur2). By the end of the nursery
353 period, all of the treatments can be assumed to be equal regarding TET-R development, and the
354 number of TET-R coliforms was lower than when pigs entered the nursery period.

355 In the present work, we provide new insights into the association between tetracycline treatment
356 regimes and development of resistance in food production animals. Our results suggest that similar
357 resistance levels are obtained no matter the duration and concentration of TET, at least under the
358 conditions used in this study, with the rigorous statis-tical approach applied and for the specific
359 treatment regimes tested.

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369

370 **Conflict of interest**

371 None to declare

372

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471 **Tables**472 **Table 1.** Tetracycline treatment regimes used in experimental and field studies.

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Study	Dose/duration (days)	Number of pigs (group)	Collection time (Day)^a	Antibiotics used for selection
Experimental	Low (5 mg/kg)/3	5 (1)	0,2,4,6,8,10,12,14,16,18	TET, no antibiotic
	High (20 mg/kg)/3	5 (2)	0,2,4,6,8,10,12,14,16,18	TET, no antibiotic
	Low (5 mg/kg)/10	5 (3)	0,2,4,6,8,10,12,14,16,18	TET, no antibiotic
	High (20 mg/kg)/10	5 (4)	0,2,4,6,8,10,12,14,16,18	TET, no antibiotic
	0/0	4 (5)	0,2,4,6,8,10,12,14,16,18	TET, no antibiotic
Field	Low (10 mg/kg)/ 6	40 (1 and 2)	SN,0,2dAT,10dAT,EN	AMP, TET, SUL, no antibiotic
	Medium (20 mg/kg)/3	40 (3 and 4)	SN,0,2dAT,10dAT,EN	AMP, TET, SUL, no antibiotic
	High (30 mg/kg)/2	40 (5 and 6)	SN,0,2dAT,10dAT,EN	AMP, TET, SUL, no antibiotic

474 ^aDay 0; day starting the treatment, day 2dAT and 10dAT: two and 10 days after having finished the
475 treatment. SN; start of nursery period, EN; end of nursery period.

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482 **Figures captions.**

483 **Figure 1. Microbiological analysis of faecal samples from pigs treated in the experimental**
484 **study with four OTC different treatment regimes.** Log₁₀CFU counts of total coliforms (a),
485 Log₁₀CFU counts of TET-R coliforms (b) and proportion of TET-R coliforms (c). Do0.Dur0; no
486 treatment administered; Do20.Dur10; high dose (20 mg/kg)–10 days regime; Do20.Dur3; high dose
487 (20 mg/kg)-three days regime; Do5.Dur10; low dose (5 mg/kg)–10 days regime; Do5.Dur3; low dose
488 (20 mg/kg)-three days regime. Discontinued vertical arrows indicate the end of the OTC treatment
489 regime. The dashed lines are 95% confidence intervals.

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491 **Figure 2. Microbiological analysis of faecal samples from pigs treated in the field study**
492 **with three different OTC treatment regimes.** Log₁₀CFU counts of total coliforms (a), Log₁₀CFU
493 counts of TET-R coliforms (b) and proportion of TET-R coliforms (c). Do10.Dur6; low dose (10
494 mg/kg)-six days regime; Do20.Dur3; medium dose (20 mg/kg)-three days regime; Do30.Dur2; high
495 dose (30 mg/kg)-two days regime. *Day 0; day starting the treatment, day 2dAT and 10dAT: two
496 and 10 days after having finished the treatment. SN; start of nursery period, EN; end of nursery period.
497 Six different symbols and six color codes are linked to each of the six treatment groups.

498

499 **Figure 3. Analysis of co-selection for AMP-R in the field study with three different OTC**
500 **treatment regimes.** Log₁₀CFU counts of AMP-R coliforms (a) and proportion of AMP-R coliforms
501 (b). Do10.Dur6; low dose (10 mg/kg)-six days regime; Do20.Dur3; medium dose (20 mg/kg)-three
502 days regime; Do30.Dur2; high dose (30 mg/kg)-two days regime. Same results were observed for co-
503 selection of SUL-R coliforms. *Day 0; day starting the treatment, day 2dAT and 10dAT: two and 10
504 days after having finished the treatment. SN; start of nursery period, EN; end of nursery period. Six
505 different symbols and six color codes are linked to each of the six treatment groups.

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508 **Figure 1**

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518 **Figure 2**

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527 **Figure 3**

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